

AGAVE AMERICANA LINN. BIOLEATHER AND ITS CHARACTERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Leather, a versatile material plays a significant role in various industries, including fashion, automotive and furniture. It is material made from the skin of an animal to make certain fashionable things like jackets, coats, boots and other accessories. The alternative source of leather is called as Bio-leather, which is also known as lab-grown leather or cultured leather. It is more environmentally friendly and cruelty-free option for leather product. *Agave americana* plant which contains more starch and fibre content is used to prepare leather material which is used as alternative for animal leather.. SEM analysis were done to study and understand the morphological properties of bio leather. Physical characteristic test such as colour, thickness, texture, Tensile strength were also studied. The antimicrobial effect was tested on two gram positive bacteria and two gram negative bacteria using zone of inhibition on solid media. These test prove that it can be used as a good alternative source for animal leather

Key words: bioleather, agave, SEM analysis, fibre, gram positive bacteria.

INTRODUCTION

Leather making is an ancient art that has been practiced for more than 7,000 years. Fresh skins were dried in the sun, softened by pounding in animal fats and brains, and preserved by salting and smoking. Beginning with simple drying and curing techniques, the process of vegetable tanning was developed by the Egyptians and Hebrews about 400 BCE. During the Mid Ages the Arabs preserved the art of leather making and so improved it that morocco and cordovan (from Córdoba, Spain) became highly prized leathers.

Bio-leather is a sustainable biomaterial derived from natural sources such as plants and microorganisms, making it environmentally friendly and biodegradable, thus helping reduce textile waste [1] According to the previous study, the general sources for bio-leather include natural latex, pineapple, mushroom, jellyfish, and bacterial cellulose (BC) [2] This study is focused on BC to develop the bio-leather. In this study, to overcome these aforementioned drawbacks, bio-leather is modified by physical entrapment of proteins, which are naturally derived materials, and are non-toxic and biodegradable [3] Proteins have shown to improve the mechanical properties of the cellulose composite material owing to their structural properties and high molecular binding potential [4]. The key characteristics and features of bio-leather include:

The synthesis of bio-leather from the plant *Agave americana*, is the weed which plays a role in its native ecosystems by providing food and habitat for pollinators, birds, and

other wildlife. The plant's deep roots help prevent soil erosion, and its ability to survive in harsh conditions contributes to ecosystem resilience. *Agave americana*, commonly known as the American agave or century plant, is a large and striking succulent native to Mexico but now cultivated worldwide for ornamental, agricultural, and commercial purposes. It is a rosette-forming plant with thick, succulent leaves that are grayish-green to blue-green in colour. The leaves are rigid, fleshy, and have sharp spines along the margins and at the tip.[5] Mature plants can reach impressive sizes, with leaves growing up to 6 to 8 feet (1.8 to 2.4 meters) long and the whole plant spanning several feet in diameter. Despite its common name "century plant," *Agave americana* typically lives for 10 to 30 years before flowering. The plant usually blooms after 10 to 30 years, producing a tall flower spike that can reach up to 30 feet (9 meters) in height. It is native to Mexico and parts of Central America. It has been introduced to other regions with similar climates and is cultivated as an ornamental plant in gardens, landscapes, and botanical collections. The leaves of *Agave americana* contain strong fibres that have been traditionally used by indigenous peoples for making ropes, mats, baskets, and textiles. The fibres are extracted through a process called decortication. [6]

The objective of the experiment on bio leather is to develop a sustainable and cruelty-free alternative to traditional leather by utilizing innovative bio-based materials and production methods. This includes investigating different sources such as plant fibres, bio-based polymers and optimizing processes for material extraction, processing, and finishing. The goal is to achieve bio leather with properties comparable to conventional leather in terms of durability, flexibility, water resistance, and aesthetic appeal. Through this experiment, we aim to contribute to reducing environmental impact, promoting ethical practices, and meeting the growing demand for sustainable materials in various industries.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Collection of *Agave americana*:-

Agave americana is commonly known as century plant or American aloe. In Tamil Nadu these plant is called as Aanaikattrazhai leaves were collected freshly from the forest area present in Mel Kaalvai, near Thiruporur, Chengalpet district.

Extraction of starch and fibre from the agave plant:-[7,8,9,10 and 11]

a. Cleaning and washing:

The collected leaves are consists of poisonous thorn at the edges of the leaves, remove the thorns with the help of the knife. Then wash the leaves clearly to remove sand particles from the leaves.

b. Peeling:-

After washing the leaves, slightly remove the upper layer of the leaves with the help of the knife. Then wash it again with the tap water. The starch was collected during peeling the leaves.

c. Extraction of fibre:-

After removing all starch from the leaves the fibres can be clearly appears at the base of the leaves. By squeezing and twisting the base layer of the leaves the fibres can be easily extract out from the unwanted layer of leaf.

d. Drying:-

The extracted fibres are dried in the sunlight for about two days which is about 32°C. It was done to remove all the moisture content and unwanted debris from the fibre.

e. Preparation of kombucha scoby:-

Materials required for scoby:

Apple cider vinegar

Hot water

Black tea bags

Sugar

Starter scoby

Bottle jar

Muslin cloth

Thread

Thermometer

SYNTHESIS OF BIO-LEATHER:-

The ingredients agave fibre and starch, PCL and distilled water at various concentration were mixed in a blender. Blend it into fine paste and filter it in the muslin cloth to remove excess starch from the fibre. Then spread the filtrate as sheet on the muslin cloth till the excess starch is filtered out from the fibre. Transfer it to the casting plate and allow them to dry for 3 to 4 hours in direct sunlight.

Mix another batch of ingredients such as kombucha scoby and PCL at different concentration in the blender. Blend all the ingredients into fine liquid and pour it on the casted fibre material and allow them to dry in 30°C.

Fabrication:-

After drying of leather sheets cut them into different shapes as per our wish. Three different samples are made at different concentration of ingredients. Then coat them with the glycerol at different concentration to avoid quick water absorption.

PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS TEST:-

Colour:

The colour was determined by the visual assessment of produced bio-leather.

Thickness of bio-leather:

The thickness of the bio-leather can be measured by using screw gauge, and the average value is calculated. The usual thickness for car or furniture leather is about 0.9 to 1.2 millimetres in thickness. The thickness of the leather can be depends on the uses, like leather used in shoes has the different measurement of thickness, whereas the leather used in the production of jacket has less thickness comparing to the shoe leather.

Tensile strength:

This test method is intended to determine the tensile properties of leather. The tensile strength test is conducted to measure the maximum stress a material can withstand before breaking under tension. First, prepare samples according to standard dimensions. Secure the sample in the testing machine grips, ensuring alignment. Apply a gradual and uniform force until the sample fractures. Record the maximum force and calculate tensile strength using the formula:

TENSILE STRENGTH (TS) = F/S

TS= tensile strength

F= the maximum force or load applied to the material during the test

S= the cross-sectional area of the material.

Maintain a controlled environment throughout the procedure to ensure consistent results.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this present study, Bio-leather is prepared by using fibre and starch of *Agave americana* plant. Three different concentration of ingredients (fibre, PCL, starch, KBC, glycerol) were used and three different bio-leather were prepared Bio-leather which is about 3.34 mm and 3.82 thickness sample were used for studying various parameters such as SEM analysis and tensile strength

SEM analysis exhibited the surface of the bio-leather produced in in this experiment. It was found to be smooth and contains little cracks which found in some places. These cracks can be occurs due to the incomplete mixing of the raw materials. The image is also shows the good adhesion between the various components such as starch, KBC scoby, PCL and glycerol of the bio-leather.

Tensile strength:Tensile strength is the amount of maximum strength to break the plastic film. Tensile strength modulus is defined as the stress change divided by change in strain within the linear viscoelastic region of the stress/strain curves. Elongation at break is the indication of the amount of the variation of extreme film length while attaining tensile strength until the film breaks, related to the original length.

Colour and texture:The colour and texture of the Bio-leather can be observed through the naked eye and the texture of the bio-leather can be determined by touching the sample.

TABLE-1: Samples made up of different concentration.

SAMPLES	FIBRE(g)	STARCH(ml)	PCL(ml)	KBC(g)	GLYCEROL(ml)
Sample-1	12	50	10	80	2
Sample-2	13	70	15	100	3
Sample-3	15	100	20	130	5

TABLE-2: Different trails made out from different concentration.

Trail	Images	Composition
T-1		Fibre – 12 g, Starch - 50 ml, KBC – 80 g, PCL – 10 ml, Glycerol - 2ml

T-2		Fibre - 13 g, Starch – 70 ml, KBC – 100 g, PCL – 15 ml, Glycerol – 3 ml
T-3		Fibre – 15 g, Starch – 100 ml, KBC – 130 ml, PCL- 20 ml, Glycerol – 5 ml

TABLE- 3: Colour and texture of the three different samples of three different measurements of components.

Colour	Texture
Black to dark brown	Hard

Plate 1: Indicates the presence of starch granules which is ovoid and less lighter in colour.

Plate 2: Tensile strength of 3.82 mm thickness and 22.41 mm width bi0-leather.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, we can determine that the bio-leather made out from the starch and fibre of the plant *Agave americana* can efficiently useful in the alternative source of animal leather. It has been successfully fabricated and characterized by various analysis such as physical and morphological characterization. The morphological characters can be analysed by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). It indicates the presence of smooth surface with small brittle structure containing starch granules and KBC granules. Thus the bio-leather can be used as the alternative for animal leather in various fashionable industries such as shoes, belt, bags, seats and leather jackets textile industries. Bio-leather contains the less toxic and degradable materials it can be able to decay faster than the animal leather. It can't cause any pollution or hazardous to the living being as well as environment. It definitely be the eco- friendly product without harming or killing any living organisms.

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